

Data set of measurement data vs test conditions for IT performance characterised in presence of separate and combined influence factors

Partner	TUD																														
Measured power quality parameter	Amplitudes of the Harmonics																														
Influence factor 1	Temperature																														
Influence factor 2 (if combined with 1)	Burden																														
Influence factor 3 (if combined with 2 and 3)	-																														
Index used to compare the reference power quality parameter with the measured power quality parameter	Harmonic ratio error defined as $\varepsilon_h = 100 \cdot \frac{k_n U_{s,h} - U_{p,h}}{U_{p,h}}$																														
Transducer under test	<p>4 IVT:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>DUT A</th> <th>DUT B</th> <th>DUT C</th> <th>DUT D</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>$U_{pri r}$</td> <td>20/$\sqrt{3}$ kV</td> <td>20/$\sqrt{3}$ kV</td> <td>35/$\sqrt{3}$ kV</td> <td>10/$\sqrt{3}$ kV</td> </tr> <tr> <td>$U_{sec r}$</td> <td>100/$\sqrt{3}$ kV</td> <td>100/$\sqrt{3}$ kV</td> <td>100/$\sqrt{3}$ kV</td> <td>100/$\sqrt{3}$ kV</td> </tr> <tr> <td>f_r</td> <td>50 Hz</td> <td>50 Hz</td> <td>50 Hz</td> <td>50 Hz</td> </tr> <tr> <td>S_r</td> <td>50 VA</td> <td>50 VA</td> <td>50 VA</td> <td>30 VA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Class</td> <td>0.5</td> <td>0.5</td> <td>0.5</td> <td>0.5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		DUT A	DUT B	DUT C	DUT D	$U_{pri r}$	20/ $\sqrt{3}$ kV	20/ $\sqrt{3}$ kV	35/ $\sqrt{3}$ kV	10/ $\sqrt{3}$ kV	$U_{sec r}$	100/ $\sqrt{3}$ kV	100/ $\sqrt{3}$ kV	100/ $\sqrt{3}$ kV	100/ $\sqrt{3}$ kV	f_r	50 Hz	50 Hz	50 Hz	50 Hz	S_r	50 VA	50 VA	50 VA	30 VA	Class	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
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Measurement procedure (short description)	<p>The frequency response is measured with a fixed fundamental with 50 Hz and 260 V and a frequency variable component with 13 V.</p> <p>The DUT's are placed in a climate chamber, after each temperature change, the thermal time constant of the DUTs is waited ten times to ensure a thermally steady state of the DUTs.</p> <p>The temperature is changed in the range -25°C to 55°C. The resistive burden is varied in seven steps in the range from 0% to 100%, the capacitive part of the burden in three steps in the range from 0 nF to 10 nF.</p>																														
Measurement Setup (short description)	<p>The generation and measurement setup is shown in the following figure.</p> <p>The fundamental and higher frequency component are together with one DAC channel of a NA 6366. The signal is amplified with a broad band amplifier (HEROPOWER</p>																														

PFL2250). The primary and secondary voltage of the are conditioned with Dewetron DAQP-HV and DAQP-LV modules and measured with two ADC-channels of the NI 6366 with a sampling rate of 600 kS/s.

Main results (tables, plots,...)

Influence of burden (constant temperature)

The resistive burden has an influence on the whole frequency range (smallest influence at rated frequency, highest influence at resonance frequency).

An additional capacitive burden has no significant influence at the fundamental frequency but increasing influence for higher frequencies.

Influence of temperature (without burden)

Change of the temperature shifts the resonance frequencies. Therefore the temperature has no significant impact on the fundamental frequency and low order harmonics. The highest impact of the temperature is in the range of the resonance frequency.

Combined influence of temperature and burden

The temperature is influencing the influence of the burden.

	<p>The graph plots accuracy error $\Delta\epsilon(f)$ (%) on the y-axis (ranging from 0 to -14) against ratio error S/S_r (%) on the x-axis (ranging from 0 to 100). There are nine data series representing combinations of frequency f and temperature T:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $f = 55$ Hz; $T = -25^\circ\text{C}$ (solid blue line with circles) $f = 55$ Hz; $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$ (dashed blue line with squares) $f = 55$ Hz; $T = 55^\circ\text{C}$ (solid blue line with diamonds) $f = 1205$ Hz; $T = -25^\circ\text{C}$ (solid red line with circles) $f = 1205$ Hz; $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$ (dashed red line with squares) $f = 1205$ Hz; $T = 55^\circ\text{C}$ (solid red line with diamonds) $f = 2555$ Hz; $T = -25^\circ\text{C}$ (solid yellow line with circles) $f = 2555$ Hz; $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$ (dashed yellow line with squares) $f = 2555$ Hz; $T = 55^\circ\text{C}$ (solid yellow line with diamonds) <p>All series show a negative correlation between ratio error and accuracy error, with the magnitude of error increasing as the ratio error increases. Higher frequencies and higher temperatures generally result in larger accuracy errors.</p>
References	=
Attached files	<p>Name: 19NRM05_IVT_burden_temperature.zip</p> <p>Description: It contains 520 csv-files, one for each frequency response under different conditions.</p> <p>The file name contains the following information: “DUT_ \$X\$ _T_ \$T\$ _\$R\$ _\$C\$”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • \$X\$: DUT name • \$T\$: temperature • \$R\$: resistive burden • \$C\$: capacitive burden <p>Each csv-file contains first a header with the DUT description and the measurement conditions containing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DUT name • Rated voltage • Accuracy class of DUT • Temperature • Resistive burden • Capacitive burden <p>The body of the csv-file contains the measured accuracy. First column: frequency in Hz, second column: ratio error in % and third column: phase displacement in °.</p>
Agree to make the data public ? (yes/no)	yes